

brown planthopper, and gall midge (Table 2). It was released for rainfed areas where water levels range from 50 to 75 cm.

PSL 60-2, a high-yielding, photoperiod-insensitive variety is from a

double cross (RDI/BR51-91-6//SPR6726-134-124/IR34). It is a semidwarf, medium-duration (130-140 d) variety with long, slender, clear grain, high amylose content, and good cooking quality. From 1983 to 1986, it averaged

4.73 t/ha, 17% higher than RDI, a standard variety (Table 1). It is resistant to sheath rot, and moderately resistant to blast, bacterial blight, and brown planthopper (Table 2). It is recommended for irrigated areas. □

Seed technology

Influence of genetic contamination on seed yield and quality of IR50

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We studied the effect of cultivar TKM9 as a contaminant on seed yield and quality in a pure seed crop of IR50 over three successive generations of seed multiplication.

Field experiments were conducted under irrigated conditions during the

dry-wet-dry seasons 1986-87. IR50 was contaminated by transplanting TKM9 at 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12% in a randomized block design. Pure seed crops of IR50 (T0) and TKM9 (T7) were included for comparison.

Levels of contamination, and seed yield and quality attributes—germination and vigor—were correlated negatively (see table). Yield potential and seed quality declined with generation advance. Yield reduction was due not only to varietal contamination, but also to loss in vigor across generations. A slow inbreeding depression in seed vigor caused a subsequent reduction in yield.

The pure seed crop of IR50 gave the highest yield, germination, and vigor in generation 1; seed yield was reduced 4.6% by generation 3. A contamination of 2% reduced yield 10.5%; 12% contamination reduced yield 42.5%. Germination and vigor declined by 7 and 20% and 24.5 and 45.4%, respectively.

Under the present system of seed production, seed is multiplied across four generations—breeder, foundation, and certified I and II. The observed reduction in seed yield and vigor by the third generation highlights the need for renewal of seed stock after 3 yr of multiplication. □

Effect of contamination on seed yield, germination, and vigor index^a under successive generations of seed multiplication in IR50. Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Generation I			Generation II			Generation III			Mean			Yield reduction after GIII (% over GI T0)
	Seed yield (g/plot)	Germination (%)	Vigor index	Seed yield (g/plot)	Germination (%)	Vigor index	Seed yield (g/plot)	Germination (%)	Vigor index	Seed yield (g/plot)	Germination (%)	Vigor index	
T0	349	93	3.0	341	92	2.9	333	89	2.5	341	91	2.8	4.6
T1	329	93	2.8	315	82	2.8	312	85	2.2	319	86	2.6	10.5
T2	321	92	2.8	311	79	2.7	306	90	2.1	312	87	2.5	13.2
T3	317	91	2.7	304	79	2.5	297	77	2.0	306	82	2.4	14.8
T4	298	91	2.7	286	78	2.4	280	73	1.7	288	81	2.3	19.9
T5	289	91	2.7	273	73	2.3	264	72	1.7	275	79	2.2	24.5
T6	257	88	2.6	209	68	2.1	201	64	1.6	222	73	2.1	42.4
T7	300	88	2.5	288	82	2.4	269	76	2.3	286	82	2.4	22.8
Mean		91	2.7	291	80	2.5	283	79	2.0				
LSD T	Seed yield			Germination			Vigor index						
G	0.01			2.25			87.9						
TxG	0.01			1.38			53.8						
	0.002			3.89			152.2						

^aVigor index = germination (%) × seedling length.

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